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A Java-DSP interface for analysis of the MP3 algorithm

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of the last decade, i.e., the Apple iPod™. The MP3 algorithm is efficient and can be used to compress the size of an audio file dramatically and the difference of quality between the original audio and the compressed audio is often not perceptible. Furthermore, Huffman coding [13] yields a variable length code (i.e.) the length of code is varied based on the data statistics. In addition, the MP3 algorithm can change its time/frequency resolution through the use of different window functions that allow better transient sound control. These features make the MP3 algorithm attractive in a variety of applications.

The MP3 encoder [17] consists of the following modules: (a) polyphase filter analysis, (b) Modified Discrete Cosine Transform (MDCT), (c) psychoacoustic model, (d) Huffman coding and (e) bit-allocation. The MPEG-1 audio codec uses a time-frequency analysis block to extract parameters from the time-domain input signal that are suitable for quantization and encoding based on perceptual criteria. The input audio stream is passed through a filter bank that divides the audio input into 32 uniformly spaced frequency subbands. The psychoacoustic module analyzes the signal, and computes the noise and signal masking as a function of frequency. In order to achieve varying temporal and frequency resolutions, based on the signal statistics, the outputs of the filter bank are processed using the MDCT. Finally, the bit allocation process determines the number of bits allocated to each of the subbands and the data is compressed to lower bit rates without loss in perception, and all of this information is added into the bitstream [16-17].

It is important to note that the decoding of the MPEG-1 bitstream is simple enough to allow single-chip, real-time decoder implementations. In this paper, we present an interactive interface developed in the Java-DSP software for study and analysis of the MP3 decoder. Note that in [18], Java-DSP modules for analysis of the MPEG-1 psychoacoustic model were presented. Figure 1 illustrates the proposed interface that displays several outputs/parameters pertinent to the algorithm. In this paper, we present several exercises developed for the undergraduate DSP class. The exercises expose students to the polyphase filter banks and use of different windows for adapting the time and frequency resolution.

2. ORGANIZATION OF THE JAVA MODULES

In this section, we describe the features of the MP3 decoder interface as implemented in Java-DSP. We use the Java-DSP environment because it can be easily used with several graphical functions which allow students to experiment with the algorithm. The plots are used to illustrate the details behind the encoding and decoding processes. The proposed interface allows frame-by-frame synthesis and provides access to the parameters evaluated at the encoder.

This MP3 decoder implementation is based on the open source software application, JLayer1.0 [19]. We have

Figure 2. The block diagram in the MP3 decoding processes.

converted the library into an applet that is compatible with Java-DSP and embedded into the software. The Java-DSP MP3 decoder includes a number of features which can display the characteristics of the different modules involved in the encoding and decoding schemes. Several visualization tools are incorporated to help students understand the working of each of these modules and the parameters used. The decoder interface reads and displays the characteristics in the header of the input MP3 file, and includes the facility to perform frame-by-frame processing.

2.1. The MP3 Decoder Interface

Figure 2 shows the window dialog of the MP3 decoder interface. The interface presents the user with a drop down menu, which has options to display the block diagram of the encoder, the decoder or the synthesis plots. The execution of the decoding can be performed in either of the two modes: (a) Auto running, (b) User preference. In the “Auto running” mode, the frames will automatically move forward slowly with a pre-defined delay. Instructors can take advantage of the pause to address the characteristics of each frame using the six plots. In the “User preference mode”, users can choose a specific frame number and the interface loads 10 frames in addition to the current frame (5 previous and 5 later frames). This helps in analyzing the characteristics of neighboring frames.

2.2. The Impulse Response of the Polyphase Filter

Efficient coding performance of a perceptual coder depends on the match between the properties of the designed filter bank and the characteristics of the input signal [20]. The filter bank used in the MP3 encoder is critically sampled or maximally decimated. The impulse response of the prototype low pass filter is shown in Figure 3. Each of the filters in the polyphase filter bank in has a modulated

Figure 3. Impulse response of the low pass filter.

Figure 4. Frequency responses of the filters.

Figure 5. Tonality of the components in the 23rd subband.

impulse response. The filters provide good time resolution with a reasonable frequency resolution. A cosine modulated pseudo-QMF M-band filter bank has a nearly perfect reconstruction and has uniform, linear phase channel responses. The prototype impulse response contains 512 samples. The modulation is done by multiplying the impulse response with a cosine of different frequency to provide a frequency shift.

2.3. Frequency Responses of the Polyphase Filters

Figure 4 illustrates the frequency responses of the filters. The response of each subband is a modulated version of the prototype response, with a cosine term to shift the lowpass response to the appropriate frequency band. The center frequencies of the subbands are the odd multiples of $\pi/64$ and the band width of each band is $\pi/32$. Though the analysis subband filter bank has very good characteristics, the lack of sharp cutoff frequencies in the subband filters can cause the spectral component of a tone to leak into an adjacent subband. Furthermore, the equal widths of the subbands do not reflect the human auditory system's frequency dependent behavior.

Figure 6. Frequency components obtained using a long window.

Figure 7. Frequency components obtained using a short window.

Figure 7. Frequency components obtained using a short window.

2.4. Tonality

The masking characteristics of tonal and non-tonal components are different and hence it becomes essential to separate them. The tonality index is hence computed as a function of frequency, which indicates the tonal nature of the spectral component. The tonality index in each partition is calculated based on whether the signal is predictable from the spectral lines in the two previous frames. Tonal components are highly predictable and hence have a relatively higher index. The psychoacoustic model estimates the JND (Just Noticeable Distortion) and removes most of the high frequency components. Most often, these high frequencies are irrelevant to human perception. Therefore, the frequency components in the middle to high frequency subbands are mostly zeros. Furthermore, it computes a likelihood measure known as the tonality index which determines if the component is more tone-like or noise-like. Figure 5 represents the tonality in the 23rd subband.

2.5. Window Switching

The MP3 algorithm needs to use several windows in order to accommodate non-stationarities. The psychoacoustic model detects the pre-echo condition and chooses short windows for better time resolution and long windows for improved frequency resolution. The type of window determines the number of coefficients in the MDCT. Figures 6 and 7 demonstrate cases (different subbands) where long windows and short windows were applied respectively. The number of frequency components also determines the frequency resolution. When long windows are used for sharper

Figure 8. The Four types of windows.

Figure 9. Three successive short windows.

transients, the signal is coarsely quantized. In the time domain, the quantization noise spreads over the entire block and it would create a perceptible noise at the beginning of the audio. Pre-echo can be controlled by detecting such transients and making a decision to switch to short windows. To maintain perfect reconstruction of MDCT, the short and long windows are not switched instantaneously. For this purpose, two transition windows, start and stop are provided. The windows used in MDCT window switching are illustrated in Figure 8 and Figure 9. It can be observed that the size of a short block is 12 samples, whereas that of a long block is 36 samples. In the short block mode, three short blocks with 50% overlap are used. Switching from a long to short window includes a transition start window while a stop window is placed in the transition from a short to a long window. Each block of data is processed by MDCT contains 36 samples.

Figure 10. Window switching and transition.

In the Java-DSP MP3 decoder interface, users can see six windows presented in the window switching plot. In fact, one frame (1152 samples) of a signal is divided into 32 subbands across frequency in the polyphase filtering process and it generates 36 time-domain samples in each subband. Two granules are formed by having 18 samples of each subband to form 576 time-frequency samples. The windowing process is applied to each granule. Therefore, each frame has two windows. We take into account switching across three frames to demonstrate window switching between granules in each frame. The current frame and two previous frames are stored and six windows are illustrated in Figure 10.

2.6. Output waveform plot

Once the decoding process is complete, the PCM audio wave file is reconstructed successfully. Figure 11 shows the final output waveform and we can use the WaveRead block in Java-DSP (which we do not describe in this paper) to see the original wave signal and we can compare the difference between the original signal and the reconstructed signal. In the case of stereo, the output waveform is changed according to which channel users select.

2.7. Frequency Domain Output

This plot shows students the output waveform in the frequency domain. Users can visualize the regions with the most energy in the frequency domain. Figure 12 illustrates an example where more frequency components lie in the low frequency region. Only few frequency components are located in the high frequency region. The signal displayed changes based on the channel selected.

3. UTILITY IN EDUCATION AND ASSESSMENT

A variety of exercises are grouped into four laboratories for use in an undergraduate signal processing course. These laboratories include analysis of the polyphase filter bank,

Figure 11. Output waveform plot.

Figure 12. Frequency Domain Output in dB.

MDCT, window switching and tonality. They can complement the teaching material, to introduce fundamentals of the MP3 algorithm, before the students actually study the complete MPEG-1 encoding/decoding system. Furthermore, the paradigm of audio coders can serve as an interesting application of the signal processing concepts taught in the course. Though the proposed decoder interface can be used a standalone tool, the J-DSP environment allows students to perform further analysis by including other signal processing functions. Figure 13 illustrates a sample J-DSP code that performs shaping of the white noise spectrum using a subband filter from the MP3 decoder interface. We will have students from the undergraduate DSP class at Arizona State University to perform these exercises and evaluate the proposed interface.

3.1 Exercise-1: Polyphase filter analysis

This exercise describes the design of the analysis filter bank used in the MP3 encoder. A low pass prototype filter is first developed; when shifted appropriately in the frequency domain, band pass filters and high pass filters can be generated. In addition, students will use the function blocks in Java-DSP to build a polyphase filterbank from scratch.

3.2 Exercise-2: MDCT Windows

In this exercise the idea of applying different windows for use in the MDCT process is demonstrated. It requires

Figure 13. An example Java-DSP simulation that performs shaping of the white noise spectrum with the subband filter response used in the MP3 algorithm.

students to measure the length of the different windows and understand the reason for using short windows. We use this exercise to explain the pre-echo occurrence and the way short windows are used to mitigate pre-echo.

3.3 Exercise-3: MDCT Frequency Components

This exercise illustrates the relationship between windows and frequency components. It requires students to observe the number of frequency components based on different windows, different frames, and different sound files. In addition, students can select different subbands and observe that most of the significant frequency components are present in low to mid-frequency subbands.

3.4 Exercise-4: Window Switching

This exercise describes the transition of window switching in neighboring frames. This experiment gives students an understanding about the order of switching windows. Different orders of windows result in different frequency components.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented tools for the analysis of the MP3 encoding and decoding process by using a sophisticated Java-DSP MP3 decoder interface. A variety of modules in the encoder and the decoder were explained through several plots embedded in the interface. A few laboratory exercises have been developed specifically for use in EEE 407 DSP class at ASU. These lab exercises show students the main ideas of each of the modules and their role in the

compression algorithm. Also a pre-quiz and post-quiz will be given to examine what students have learned about MP3 by using the Java-DSP MP3 simulation tool.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] The Java-DSP web-page [on-line]; MIDL LAB, Arizona State University: <http://jdsp.asu.edu>.
- [2] A. Spanias, *Digital Signal Processing; An Interactive Approach*, ISBN: 978-1-4243-2524-5, Publisher LuLu.com, September 2007.
- [3] A. Clausen, A. Spanias, and A. Xavier, "A Java signal analysis tool for signal processing experiments," in *Proc. of 1998 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics Speech and Signal Processing*, pp. 1849-1852, vol. 3, May 1998, Seattle.
- [4] A. Spanias et. al, "Development of a web-based signal and speech processing laboratory for distance learning," *ASEE Computers in Education Journal*, pp. 21-26, vol. X, no.2, April-June 2000.
- [5] A. Spanias, and V. Atti, "Interactive on-line undergraduate laboratories using Java-DSP," in *IEEE Trans. on Education Special Issue on Web-based Instruction*, pp. 735-749, vol. 48, no. 4, Nov. 2005.
- [6] V. Atti, and A. Spanias, "On-line simulation modules for teaching speech and audio compression," in *Proc. of IEEE Frontiers in Education (FIE-2003)*, pp. T4E-17 - T4E-22, vol. 1, Nov 5-8, 2003, Boulder.
- [7] V. Atti, A. Spanias, C. Panayiotou, and Y. Song, "Teaching digital filter design techniques used in high-fidelity audio applications," in *Proc. of ASEE-2004 Conference*, June 20-23, 2004, Salt Lake City, Utah.
- [8] M. Yasin, L. J. Karam, and A. Spanias, "On-line laboratories for image and two-dimensional signal processing," in *Proceedings of IEEE Frontiers in Education (FIE-2003)*, Nov. 2003, Boulder.
- [9] T. Thrasyvoulou, K. Tsakalis and A. Spanias, "J-DSP-C, A Control Systems Simulation Environment For Distance Learning: Labs And Assessment," in *Proceedings Of 33rd ASEE/IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference*, Boulder, CO, November 5-8, 2003.
- [10] M. Zaman, A. Papandreou-Suppappola and A. Spanias, "Advanced concepts in time-frequency signal processing made simple", in *Frontiers in Education Conference*, November 2003.
- [11] Y. Ko, T. Duman, and A. Spanias, "J-DSP for communications," 33rd ASEE/IEEE FIE Conference, Boulder, November 2003.
- [12] K. Ramamurthy, A. Spanias, L. Hinnov, and J. Ogg, "On the use of J-DSP in Earth systems," *Proceedings of ASEE Annual Conference and Exposition*, Pittsburgh, PA, June 2008.
- [13] A. Spanias, Ted Painter, and V. Atti, *Audio Signal Processing and Coding*, Wiley, 2007.
- [14] J. J. Thiagarajan and A. Spanias, *Analysis of the MPEG-1 Layer-III Algorithm using MATLAB Software* (Book in final preparation).
- [15] K. N. Ramamurthy and A. Spanias, *MATLAB Software for the Code Excited Linear Prediction Algorithm: The Federal Standard-1016*, Morgan & Claypool publishers, 2010.
- [16] ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG11, "Information Technology – Coding of Moving Pictures and Associated Audio for Digital Storage Media at up to about 1.5 Mbit/sec–IS 11172-3:Audio", 1992.
- [17] K. Salomonsen, S. Sogaard, E.P. Larsen, "Design and Implementation of an MPEG/Audio," Dept. Comm. Tech., Inst. Elect. System, 1997.
- [18] Y. Song, A. Spanias, V. Atti, and V. Berisha, "Interactive Java modules for the MPEG-1 psychoacoustic model," in *Proc. of 2005 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, pp. 581-584, vol 5, March 18-23, 2005.
- [19] [J]Zoom web-page: <http://www.javazoom.net>
- [20] R. Rangachar, A. Spanias, "A simulation tool for introducing MPEG-audio (MP3) concepts in a DSP course", in *Proc. of 2002 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics Speech and Signal Processing*, pp. 4116-4119, vol. 4, May 2002, Florida.